

COMPARATIVE EFFICACY OF INHALED CORTICOSTEROIDS OF DIFFERENT MODES OF ACTION IN RECURRENT LARYNGOTRACHEITIS IN CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

Recurrent laryngotracheitis in children is a pressing clinical and social problem in pediatrics and otolaryngology due to the high frequency of recurrent episodes, the risk of developing laryngeal stenosis, and respiratory dysfunction. Persistent inflammation of the upper respiratory tract mucosa plays a leading role in the pathogenesis of the disease, accompanied by edema, hypersecretion, and impaired local defense mechanisms. Inhaled corticosteroids are widely used for inflammatory respiratory diseases, but data on their comparative efficacy in recurrent laryngotracheitis remain limited and require further clarification.

Introduction

Recurrent laryngotracheitis in children is a pressing clinical and social problem in pediatrics and otolaryngology due to the high frequency of recurrent episodes, the risk of developing laryngeal stenosis, and respiratory dysfunction. Persistent inflammation of the upper respiratory tract mucosa plays a leading role in the pathogenesis of the disease, accompanied by edema, hypersecretion, and impaired local defense mechanisms. Inhaled corticosteroids are widely used for inflammatory respiratory diseases, but data on their comparative efficacy in recurrent laryngotracheitis remain limited and require further clarification.

Purpose of the study

To evaluate the comparative clinical efficacy and safety of inhaled corticosteroids of various pharmacological groups in recurrent laryngotracheitis in children.

Materials and methods

A prospective comparative clinical trial was conducted involving 90 children aged 1 to 5 years with recurrent laryngotracheitis. Patients were divided into three comparable groups of 30 each and received budesonide, fluticasone, or beclomethasone at age-appropriate therapeutic doses by inhalation for 12 weeks. Treatment efficacy was assessed based on the frequency of relapses, the severity of clinical symptoms, and the need for hospitalization.

Results and discussion

The study found that the use of inhaled corticosteroids in all groups was associated with a reduced relapse rate of recurrent laryngotracheitis and a reduction in the severity of clinical symptoms. The most pronounced clinical effect was observed in the budesonide group, where

the relapse rate decreased by an average of 45%, accompanied by a rapid regression of inspiratory stridor and barking cough. In the fluticasone group, the relapse rate decreased by approximately 40%, with clinical improvement being more gradual. Patients receiving beclomethasone experienced a moderate reduction in the frequency of exacerbations (approximately 30%), but the statistical significance of the differences compared to baseline values was less pronounced. These data indicate differences in the clinical efficacy of ICS, which is likely related to their pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic properties.

Conclusions

1. Inhaled corticosteroids are effective anti-relapse therapy for recurrent laryngotracheitis in children. 2. Budesonide demonstrated the most pronounced clinical effect, making it a first-line drug for children with frequent relapses. 3. Fluticasone has high anti-inflammatory activity and can be used as an alternative therapy. 4. Beclomethasone has a moderate clinical effect and is appropriate as part of combination therapy.

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